

A GENERALIZATION OF CONGRUENCE PROPERTIES FOR A RESTRICTED PARTITION FUNCTION

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Abstract

A 1989 result of Y. H. H. Kwong established periodicity of the sequence of values of the restricted partition function $p(n, m)$ modulo any natural number where $p(n, m)$ enumerates partitions of n into at most m parts. In this paper we re-visit this result and establish several new and general theorems on infinite families of partition congruences.

1. Introduction

A partition of an integer n is a finite sequence of non-increasing natural numbers $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k$ such that $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \dots + \lambda_k = n$. Each λ_i is called a part of the partition. The general partition function is denoted by $p(n)$. In 1919, Ramanujan [12] observed and proved several congruence properties for the general partition function. The most most basic of these are

$$p(5n + 4) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \quad p(7n + 5) \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$$

and $p(11n + 6) \equiv 0 \pmod{11}$.

In 2000 Ono [11] proved that for any prime $\ell \geq 5$, there exist infinitely many partition congruences with the form $p(An + B) \equiv 0 \pmod{\ell}$. With the assistance of Rhiannon Weaver [3], an undergraduate student at the time, they were able to compute many examples of Ono's results. Here is one example:

$$p(4063467631n + 30064597) \equiv 0 \pmod{31}.$$

Ono's partition divisibility results were extended by Ahlgren [1] to any prime power ℓ^a later in that year. Recent work of Yifan Yang [13] continues in this vein.

The restricted partition function, $p(n, m)$, defined as the number of partitions of n into at most m parts, was studied by Euler as an auxiliary partition function

in his investigation into the general partition function. It was also a focus of J. J. Sylvester’s work on invariant theory in the 19th century [4].

For $m \geq n$, we have the relation $p(n, m) = p(n)$. If n is negative, we define $p(n, m) = 0$, and $p(0, m) = 1$. Kronholm [5, 6, 7] and Larsen [8] have proven Ramanujan-style divisibility properties similar to those proved by Ono and Ahlgren for this restricted partition function. Here are several specific examples of congruences for $p(n, m)$.

Example 1. For $k \geq 0$ one has

$$p(54k - 3, 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{27} \tag{1}$$

$$p(60k - 5, 5) \equiv p(60k - 10, 5) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}. \tag{2}$$

and

$$p(2940k - 7, 7) \equiv 0 \pmod{49}. \tag{3}$$

In order to state such results in their full generality in Theorem 1 we require the following definition.

Definition 1 ([6]). For any natural number a , we denote by $lcm(a)$ the least common multiple of the natural numbers from 1 to a .

Theorem 1 ([7]). For ℓ an odd prime, $k \geq 0$, $1 \leq j \leq \frac{\ell - 1}{2}$, and $\alpha \geq 1$,

$$p(lcm(\ell)\ell^{\alpha-1}k - j\ell, \ell) \equiv 0 \pmod{\ell^\alpha}.$$

We note that the congruence results of Theorem 1 are dependent on a prime number of parts ℓ and confined to some power of that same prime. The main goal of this paper is to establish results similar to Theorem 1 without any restrictions on the number of parts or the modulus. In order to do this we will make use of Theorem 2 and Theorem 3 which describe the periodicity of sequences of integer partitions of the form $\{p(n, m) \pmod{j}\}_{n \geq 0}$. Indeed, such periodicity results can be recast as divisibility patterns. However, we obtain several infinite families of partition congruences of the form $p(Ak + B, m) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}$ that, while dependent on established periodicity results, they are by no means immediate and overt. Moreover, the results of this paper are different than those displayed in Example 1 and Theorem 1 in that there are no restrictions on the number of parts m or the modulus j .

2. Background

It is well known that the generating function for $p(n, m)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n, m)q^n = \frac{1}{(1 - q)(1 - q^2)\dots(1 - q^m)}. \tag{4}$$

Definition 2. A sequence $\{a_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is *purely periodic* modulo a positive integer M if there exists a positive integer μ such that $a_{n+\mu} \equiv a_n \pmod{M}$ for $n \geq 0$. The smallest such μ is called the minimum period.

Nijenhuis and Wilf [10] described the periodicity of $p(n, m)$ modulo a prime. In 1989, Kwong [9] extended these results by proving that for fixed m , the restricted partition function is purely periodic modulo a power of a prime.

Theorem 2 (Kwong). [9] Let ℓ, m, N and $b \geq 1$ be integers with ℓ prime and b the least integer such that $\ell^b \geq \sum_{\delta \geq 0} \phi(\ell^\delta) \left\lfloor \frac{m}{\ell^\delta} \right\rfloor$ where ϕ is Euler's totient function.

Furthermore, let L be the ℓ -free part of $\text{lcm}(m)$ as in Definition 1. Then $\{p(n, m) \pmod{\ell^N}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is purely periodic with minimum period $\ell^{N+b-1}L$.

Kwong also proved a result that allows us to extend this to modulo any positive integer j .

Theorem 3 (Kwong). [9] Let $\mu(M)$ be the minimum period of an infinite integer sequence modulo any positive integer $M > 1$. If $M = \ell_1^{e_1} \ell_2^{e_2} \dots \ell_s^{e_s}$ is the prime factorization of M , then $\mu(M) = \text{lcm}(\mu(\ell_1^{e_1}), \mu(\ell_2^{e_2}), \dots, \mu(\ell_s^{e_s}))$.

Kwong's two theorems enable us to compute the minimum period of the restricted partition function modulo j given a fixed number of parts m . We denote this period as $\mu(m, j)$.

Remark 1. Statements of periodicity modulo j can be readily translated into infinite families of divisibility properties in the following way: For $0 \leq s < \mu(m, j)$ and integers t and k , whenever $p(s, m) \equiv t \pmod{j}$, then, for all $k \geq 0$, one has $p(\mu(m, j)k + s, m) \equiv t \pmod{j}$.

Some of the tools we will use in establishing our results are reciprocal polynomials and anti-reciprocal polynomials which we now define.

Definition 3. [2] A polynomial $P(q) = a_0 + a_1q + \dots + a_dq^d$ is called *reciprocal* if for each $i, a_i = a_{d-i}$; equivalently, $q^d P\left(\frac{1}{q}\right) = P(q)$.

Definition 4. [5] A polynomial $P(q) = a_0 + a_1q + \dots + a_dq^d$ is called *anti-reciprocal* if for each $i, a_i = -a_{d-i}$; equivalently, $q^d P\left(\frac{1}{q}\right) = -P(q)$.

The remainder of this paper investigates the instances of s , with $0 \leq s < \mu(m, j)$, for which $p(s, m) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}$ and thereby establishing several new infinite families of partition congruences overlooked by the periodicity results of Kwong. It is important to note that the minimum period $\mu(m, j)$ is describing "pure periodicity" whereas $\text{lcm}(m)$, as it is used in Theorem 1, is describing a different and shorter *sub*-period.

3. Results

3.1. Congruences in an Arithmetic Progression for a Fixed Number of Parts

Theorem 4. *Modulo j , $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [p(n, m) - p(n - \mu(m, j), m)]q^n$ is a polynomial of degree $\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}$. If m is even, it is an anti-reciprocal polynomial; if m is odd, it is a reciprocal polynomial.*

Proof. From Equation (4) we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [p(n, m) - p(n - \mu(m, j), m)]q^n = \frac{1 - q^{\mu(m, j)}}{(1 - q)(1 - q^2)\dots(1 - q^m)}. \tag{5}$$

Theorem 2 guarantees that modulo j , (5) is a polynomial.

We will use definitions 3 and 4 to show that modulo j , the right-hand side of (5) is either a reciprocal or antireciprocal polynomial of degree $d = \mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}$. We begin by setting

$$P(q) \equiv \frac{1 - q^{\mu(m, j)}}{(1 - q)(1 - q^2)\dots(1 - q^m)} \pmod{j}$$

for $P(q)$ the polynomial in question of degree $d = \mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}$.

$$\begin{aligned} q^d P\left(\frac{1}{q}\right) &\equiv \frac{q^{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}} (1 - q^{-\mu(m, j)})}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{q}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{q^2}\right) \dots \left(1 - \frac{1}{q^m}\right)} \equiv \frac{q^{\mu(m, j)} - 1}{q^{\binom{m+1}{2}} \left(\frac{q-1}{q}\right) \left(\frac{q^2-1}{q^2}\right) \dots \left(\frac{q^m-1}{q^m}\right)} \\ &\equiv \frac{q^{\mu(m, j)} - 1}{(q-1)(q^2-1)\dots(q^m-1)} \equiv (-1)^{m+1} \frac{1 - q^{\mu(m, j)}}{(1 - q)(1 - q^2)\dots(1 - q^m)} \equiv \pm P(q) \pmod{j}. \end{aligned}$$

The sign on the final equivalence depends on m even or odd. □

Corollary 1. *For $\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} < s < \mu(m, j)$ one has $p(\mu(m, j)k + s, m) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}$.*

Proof. Observe that

$$P(q) \equiv p(0, m) + p(1, m)q + \dots + p(\mu(m, j) - 1, m)q^{\mu(m, j) - 1} \pmod{j}. \tag{4}$$

Since it is an (anti)reciprocal polynomial of degree $\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}$ we can rewrite (4) as

$$P(q) \equiv p(0, m) + p(1, m)q + \dots + p\left(\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}, m\right)q^{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}} \pmod{j}.$$

Note that $\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} < \mu(m, j) - 1$, so each coefficient on the terms q with exponents between $\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}$ and $\mu(m, j) - 1$ must be 0 (mod j). Hence, we have

$$p\left(\mu(m, j)k - \binom{m+1}{2} + 1, m\right) \equiv p\left(\mu(m, j)k - \binom{m+1}{2} + 2, m\right) \equiv \dots \\ \dots \equiv p(\mu(m, j)k - 1, m) \equiv 0 \pmod{j},$$

which proves the corollary. □

Here are some examples to illustrate Corollary 1.

Example 2. For $m = 6$ and $j = 4$, $\mu(m, j) = \mu(6, 4) = 480$ and $\binom{m+1}{2} = \binom{7}{2} = 21$; hence,

$$p(480k - 20, 6) \equiv p(480k - 19, 6) \equiv \dots \equiv p(480k - 1, 6) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}.$$

For $m = 5$ and $j = 5$, $\mu(m, j) = \mu(5, 5) = 300$ and $\binom{m+1}{2} = \binom{6}{2} = 15$; hence,

$$p(300k - 14, 5) \equiv p(300k - 13, 5) \equiv \dots \equiv p(300k - 1, 5) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}.$$

For $m = 8$ and $j = 3$, $\mu(m, j) = \mu(8, 3) = 7560$ and $\binom{m+1}{2} = \binom{9}{2} = 36$; hence,

$$p(7560k - 35, 8) \equiv p(7560k - 34, 8) \equiv \dots \equiv p(7560k - 1, 8) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}.$$

Corollary 2. For $k \geq 0$, $h \geq 0$, and $0 \leq s < \mu(m, j)$, if m is even one has

$$p(\mu(m, j)k + s, m) \equiv -p\left(\mu(m, j)h + \mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} - s, m\right) \pmod{j}$$

and if m is odd one has

$$p(\mu(m, j)k + s, m) \equiv p\left(\mu(m, j)h + \mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} - s, m\right) \pmod{j}.$$

Proof. By Theorem 4, for m even, it follows that

$$p(s, m) \equiv -p\left(\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} - s, m\right) \pmod{j}$$

when $0 \leq s \leq \mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}$. Note that $-p(\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} - s, m) = 0$ when $s > \mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}$. By Corollary 1, for $\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} < s < \mu(m, j)$ we have that $p(s, m) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}$. Thus, for $\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} < s < \mu(m, j)$,

$$p(s, m) \equiv -p\left(\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} - s, m\right) \pmod{j}.$$

This proves the case for m even by Remark 1. A similar argument holds for the case where m is odd. □

Using this corollary and taking Definition 4 into consideration, we can further prove interesting results.

Proposition 1. *If $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ and j is odd then*

$$p\left(\mu(m, j)k + \frac{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}}{2}, m\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}$$

and if j is even then

$$p\left(\mu(m, j)k + \frac{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}}{2}, m\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{j/2}. \tag{5}$$

Proof. Note that $(\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2})/2$ is an integer when $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. By Corollary 2, we can say

$$\begin{aligned} p\left(\frac{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}}{2}, m\right) &\equiv -p\left(\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2} - \frac{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}}{2}, m\right) \\ &\equiv -p\left(\frac{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}}{2}, m\right) \pmod{j} \end{aligned}$$

and arrive at

$$2p\left(\frac{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}}{2}, m\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}.$$

If j is odd then the $\gcd(2, j) = 1$, hence

$$p\left(\frac{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}}{2}, m\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}.$$

If j is even then the $\gcd(2, j) = 2$, and hence

$$p\left(\frac{\mu(m, j) - \binom{m+1}{2}}{2}, m\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{j/2}.$$

Thus the proposition follows. □

Here are some examples of Proposition 3.4

Example 3. For $k \geq 0$ one has $p(60k + 25, 4) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, $p(7560k + 3762, 8) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $p(48k + 19, 4) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$.

3.2. Congruences in an Arithmetic Progression for a Small Family of Number of Parts

The following theorem deals with variability across the second variable, m , rather than the first one. It is similar to a theorem proved by Kronholm [6].

Theorem 5. For $k \geq 0$ and $2 \leq t \leq m$ and $1 \leq c < \binom{t+1}{2}$

$$p(\mu(m, j)k - c, t) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}.$$

We require the following lemma.

Lemma 1. For $1 \leq t \leq m$ and x is a natural number, we have that $\mu(m, j) = x\mu(t, j)$.

Proof. The cases $t = 1$ and $t = m$ are trivial. When $t = 1$ then $\mu(1, j) = 1$ so $x = \mu(m, j)$. When $t = m$ then $\mu(t, j) = \mu(m, j)$ so $x = 1$.

We consider $2 \leq t < m$. Let $j = p_1^{e_1} p_2^{e_2} \dots p_s^{e_s}$ be the prime factorization of j as in Theorem 3 so that for t, m and j we have

$$\mu(t, j) = \text{lcm}\{\mu(t, p_1^{e_1}), \mu(t, p_2^{e_2}), \dots, \mu(t, p_s^{e_s})\} \tag{6}$$

and

$$\mu(m, j) = \text{lcm}\{\mu(m, p_1^{e_1}), \mu(m, p_2^{e_2}), \dots, \mu(m, p_s^{e_s})\}. \tag{7}$$

From Theorem 2, we have for any natural number a ,

$$\mu(a, p_i^{e_i}) = p_i^{e_i + b_{a,i} - 1} L_{a,p_i} \tag{8}$$

where $b_{a,i}$ is the least integer such that $p_i^{b_{a,i}} \geq \sum_{\delta \geq 0} \phi(p_i^\delta) \left\lfloor \frac{a}{p_i^\delta} \right\rfloor$ and L_{a,p_i} is the p_i -free part of $\text{lcm}(a)$.

With $2 \leq t < m$ and Definition 1, it is clear that $\text{lcm}(t) | \text{lcm}(m)$. Moreover, from the definition of L from Theorem 3 and (8) that for every $p_i | j$, if p_i^g is the largest power of p_i dividing $\text{lcm}(m)$, then $\text{lcm}(t)$ cannot have a larger power of p_i dividing it. It then follows that for every $p_i | j$,

$$L_{t,p_i} | L_{m,p_i}. \tag{9}$$

Furthermore, with $2 \leq t < m$ and the definition of b from Theorem 3 and (8) it is clear that $b_{t,i} \leq b_{m,i}$. Hence for every $p_i | j$,

$$p_i^{b_{t,i}} | p_i^{b_{m,i}}. \tag{10}$$

Now, lines (9) and (10) together with (6) and (7) imply that $\mu(t, j) | \mu(m, j)$. Thus, $\mu(m, j) = x\mu(t, j)$ for some natural number x . \square

We now prove Theorem 5.

Proof. By Lemma 1, for $2 \leq t \leq m$, there exists an integer x such that $\mu(m, j) = x\mu(t, j)$. Also, by Corollary 2, for $1 \leq c < \binom{t+1}{2}$

$$p(\mu(t, j)k - c, t) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}.$$

By Remarks 1 we can say that $p((x - 1)\mu(t, j)k + \mu(t, j)k - c, t) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}$, $p(x\mu(t, j)k - c, t) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}$, and $p(\mu(m, j)k - c, t) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}$. \square

Example 4 serves to highlight the nature of Theorem 5; that these divisibility results are not confined to a fixed number of parts m . In Theorem 5 set $m = 6$ and $j = 10$ so that $\mu(m, j) = \mu(6, 10) = 1200$ and $1 \leq c < \binom{6+1}{2}$. For the family of numbers of parts t with $2 \leq t \leq 6$ we have the following list of congruences in (11).

Example 4.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(1200k - 1, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 2 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 2, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 2 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 3, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 3 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 4, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 3 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 5, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 3 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 6, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 4 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 7, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 4 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 8, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 4 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 9, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 4 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 10, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 5 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 11, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 5 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 12, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 5 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 13, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 5 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 14, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & 5 \leq t \leq 6 \\
 p(1200k - 15, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & t = 6 \\
 p(1200k - 16, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & t = 6 \\
 p(1200k - 17, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & t = 6 \\
 p(1200k - 18, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & t = 6 \\
 p(1200k - 19, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & t = 6 \\
 p(1200k - 20, t) &\equiv 0 \pmod{10} & t = 6.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

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